

Introduction

The primary objective of this study is to predict accurately the amplitudes and wave forms of low frequency gravity waves in the atmosphere and the ionosphere, which are produced by earthquakes and explosions. Since these waves, which increase in amplitude with altitude because of the decreasing density of the atmosphere with height, will produce relatively large fluctuations in the electron densities in the ionosphere, the disturbance can be sensed by standard electromagnetic sounding techniques. Hence, sensitive monitoring of seismically produced atmospheric disturbances can be accomplished by EM sounding methods. An objective of this study is, therefore, to produce predictions of the atmospheric ionospheric disturbances to be expected from different kinds of shallow seismic sources. Such predictive capabilities provide a framework for studying the properties of the atmosphere and ionosphere using gravity wave excitation produced by large seismic sources.

Near-surface sources can produce waves in the atmosphere having two principal components at long distances from the source, an acoustic wave with relatively high frequencies and a gravity wave with lower frequencies. Atmospheric and ionospheric disturbances due to seismic sources have been observed by numerous techniques and experiments. A review of the earlier observations is given by Blanc (1985), where earthquakes and volcanic eruptions were found to have produced atmospheric and ionospheric disturbances both near to, and very far from, their epicenters (Davies and Baker, 1965). In several early studies, nuclear explosions in the atmosphere were observed through their ionospheric effects (Beynon and Jones, 1962; Baker and Davies, 1968; Francis, 1975). There have also been recent observations of acoustic-gravity waves in the thermosphere and in the ionosphere following space shuttle ascents (Jacobson and Carlos, 1994).

Electromagnetic sounding of the ionosphere after surface explosions has concentrated on the initial acoustic response to the blast wave in the local region around the source (e.g., Blanc and Rickel, 1989). However, a surface chemical explosion of 5 kilotons (ANFO) was observed to excite 6 min oscillations of the ionosphere that lasted for about 1 h (Jacobson et al., 1988). Kanamori et al. (1994) have evaluated observations for several

major volcanic eruptions and have found 5-min oscillations recorded near the Mt. St. Helens and Krakatoa volcanic eruptions with amplitudes of 0.3 mbar and 2 mbar respectively. Further, larger scale ionospheric motions, produced by long period gravity waves from earthquakes and subsurface nuclear explosions, are likely to be responsible for the observations of electromagnetic signals reported by Gokhberg et al. (1990).

The significance of the 5-min oscillations is that this period closely corresponds to the theoretical Brunt–Vaisala period; that is, it is near to the theoretical minimum period for internal gravity wave oscillations in the atmosphere, for its particular density decrease with height. Extensive observations of the distribution of gravity waves, both in frequency and horizontal wave number space, indicate that the observed minimum period at the shorter wavelengths is, in fact, 5 min (Manson, 1990). Likewise, the observed frequency distribution of gravity waves has been shown to be a consequence of both wave growth, due to decreasing atmospheric density with height, and wave dissipation (c.f. Imamura and Ogawa, 1995).

Since observations of zonal winds at 86 km altitude have shown that the background energy is a minimum at the Brunt–Vaisala frequency, with a spectral slope of about $-5/3$ for frequencies higher than those in the tidal band (Fritts, 1984), it follows that the 5 to 10 min period band is relatively noiseless and so gravity waves in this period range should be more readily observable. In this regard, recent observations and analysis of nightglow and noctilucent clouds at 80 to 130 km altitudes has allowed the direct observation of such waves (c.f. Gardner (1995), and associated papers). In addition, since gravity waves refract along the Earth's surface, they are observed at greater horizontal distances than the acoustic wave (Francis, 1975). Thus, it is evident from the standpoint of detectability that the 5 to 10 min period gravity wave produced by a seismic source will be the most easily measured at high altitudes near the source.

As noted above, it has been demonstrated that wave growth, due to the decrease with altitude of the density of the atmosphere, occurs exponentially with a lower scale height of about 8 km, and it is also known that this growth is counteracted by damping due to radiation and molecular diffusion processes below the ionosphere, with the damping magnitude being dependent on the frequency and wavelengths of the internal gravity wave (Imamura and Ogawa, 1995). However, gravity waves near the Brunt–Vaisala frequency, and of shorter wavelength, are less

affected by these damping processes and can grow to a saturation point where wave-breaking with viscous damping and other nonlinear processes can occur. Observations indicate that the saturation amplitudes of the internal gravity waves, occurring at about 80 km, are approximately 10% of the background fluctuations in the temperature and pressure fields at that altitude, with the gravity wave amplitude decreasing above this altitude (Fritts, 1984). Further, the dissipative forces are found to be such that short-duration sources produce far-field gravity waves with wavetrains from 1 to 2 h in duration. In the non-linear modeling developed in the present study, we will incorporate specific damping mechanisms and compare predicted results with observations in order to confirm that the modeling reproduces observations.

Based on partial confirmation of the non-linear numerical modeling by these limited observational results and verified, albeit approximate, analytical results, we will use predictions of amplitudes and wave characteristics in the time domain to evaluate the possibilities for observational studies using particular atmospheric and ionospheric gravity wave detection methods. In this regard, we compare correlations between the non-linear gravity wave predictions of this study and the GPS detections of ionospheric perturbations obtained by Calais and Minster (1995) following the large January 17, 1994 Northridge earthquake in order to try to establish a framework for further investigations.